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Apprenticeship Reform in France

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Introduction

Amazingly the reform of apprenticeship is coming after the first growth of apprenticeship after ten years (7,4% in 2017!), making probably more difficult the analysis of its effects.

Is the reform answering the criticisms and aligning French apprenticeship on the best in class systems and on EU VET objectives?

At the first reading the reform appears like a list 20 different measures without hierarchy, making it hardly decipherable, going from an increase of 30,00 € per month of apprentice payment (first measure) to the enlargement of maximum apprentice age from 25 to 30. Can we find the top 5 “iconic” measures of that list?

1. Any alternating contracts will be funded.
2. The learning funding system will be fully reviewed, using a simple, transparent and secure principle: a youth + a company = a contract = a financing. All contracts will be funded in all sectors regardless of the size of the company.
3. The search for a business by a young person will no longer face the problem of financing the contract.
4. The hiring aids will be unified and focused on the small and very small companies and the lowest qualification levels.
5. The hiring of apprentices can be done throughout the year and will be much less constrained by the school pace.
6. The governance of apprenticeship will be withdrawn to regions for the benefit of professional branches
7. Apprenticeship schools will be funded contract by contract and not globally.

Apprenticeship reform hits

If we look into more details to the reform, we must emphasize the following points:

The basic objective is to increase apprenticeship numbers by an optimization of funds and by aligning diplomas with professional branch’s needs.

As if there is no real reference to it, is it making echo to the EU objective for 2020: “VET systems should be more attractive and accessible to all, providing quality education with high labour market relevance. They must be flexible enough to allow permeability between the different education systems...”?

As an answer, the age limit to sign an apprenticeship contract is pushed from 25 to 30 and apprentices will have the possibility to enter into their training all along the year, out of school periods.

Contract duration can be adapted in regards of trainee existing competences. The minimum duration of an apprenticeship contract is 6 months instead of 1 year. Apprenticeship contract

Figure 2 Governance after reform

Is the Apprenticeship reform answering both French and EU objectives?

The French reform doesn't make any reference to European Union objectives but amazingly we can't help recognizing some nearness.

We can summarize the reproaches made to the previous system: too complex tax and subsidies, lack of flexibility of the system (mainly the rhythm of courses/ companies work organization), inadequate content of courses in regard of company's needs, huge complexity and inefficiency of apprenticeship governance, low attractiveness for students. Last but not least, the negative influence of National Education was pointed out.

The first answer is matching France and EU VET attractiveness objectives "making initial VET an attractive learning option and fostering the excellence, quality and relevance of VET to the labour market".

Many iconic measures are answering this objective:

- "1 employer + 1 apprentice = 1 funded contract" is creating a mandatory link between labour market and apprenticeship. It clearly appears that this principle is excluding VET without a link to labour market;
- orientation is not left at the National Education but at the regions as they know manpower needs in their areas. Many blames were weighing on the lack of consideration of NE regarding apprenticeship, so we can expect some improvement in VET attractiveness;
- professional branches leadership on CFA creation. This is probably the key measure of the reform. Until now the collected taxes went to the regions that redistributed it to their schools. The new system is much simpler: the schools are paid for each apprenticeship contract. This is the end of an obscure system made of political subsidies. Until now the regions could maintain the activity of their local schools for political considerations, with the new system the only survivors will be the schools answering real manpower needs as if an envelope of 250 M€ will be maintained to balance some critical cases in the regions. Professional branches become the pivot point of professional world in apprenticeship system. But amazingly, becoming a school delivering VET is now opened to all training companies. The positive contribution of these new comers will be innovative learning and challenging some existing positions.

- Designing of VET diplomas is now a prerogative of professional branches to the detriment of NE.

The employability of graduates is the marker of the reform. From a student perspective it is reinforcing the attractiveness of apprenticeship that becomes the way to a job with a very limited risk of unemployment.

The second answer aligned with EU objectives is about flexibility and simplifying access to training and qualifications.

Three measures can be pulled out to illustrate the effort to improve flexibility:

- the possibility to enter into apprenticeship at any time during the year, the rigidity of scholar agenda being one of the main brakes to company's collaboration.
- some decrees will be published to enlarge access conditions to apprenticeship for unemployed and people living with minimum social wage in a « difficult area ». Without delay an inter-ministerial delegate has been nominated to support apprenticeship in popular areas. One of his missions will be to align local competences with companies needs via apprenticeship.
- for young with a lack of basic competences (writing, reading...) a preparation course will be created upstream the apprenticeship courses. Moreover, as aids are now focused on lowest qualifications we can hope that apprenticeship will return to its initial vocation instead of growing on the highest levels.

The simplification of incentive and tax systems but also of registration process are reinforcing the strategy of facilitating access to VET.

The international mobility in VET, an EU objective, is also encouraged by the new law with the introduction of a pan European measure allowing to follow a part of the training abroad.

The quality of training of CFA, again an EU objective, will be piloted via a unique system of control and certification under France Compétences responsibility. National Education is also losing here a part of its autonomy.

Were the European Union objectives for VET a consistent guideline for France?

If we look wording and objectives, we can be struck by their convergence as if it was not publicly expressed.

The French reform is offering an interesting declension with concrete answers. On the other side it would be amazing to see if those solutions could be applicable in European countries facing the same challenges...

The main logic of the reform is to give the leadership to professional branches and create a competition environment to ensure employment opportunities after VET.

Still in the competition mind, it will be very interesting to see how IVET and CVET² will work together and/or compete. With 665 000 IVET students in 1500 schools on one side (National Education) and 430 000 CVET apprentices in 950 CFA on the other side (Professional branches) we can hope the new law will be challenging and improve their offer.

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Minutes

The debate about the French reform of apprenticeship has raised a major question, « is the objective (increasing apprenticeship number) justifying the methods » ? In French we say « the end justifies the means » and behind this question the second question could be a deeper one, **what should we save from apprenticeship to maintain its vocational spirit.**

Before trying to answer this debate two things from the debate must be specified:

- The apprenticeship reform we discuss here is focused on CVET and doesn't include National Education path as these paths are not under an employment contract condition. It doesn't include either the past professionalization period system and professionalization contract (as if they have been modified by the reform). The difference between National Education new strategy regarding professionalization and Professional branches strategy regarding apprenticeship will be an exciting subject of study.
- **The apprenticeship reform is answering most of the drawback of past French system**, most of the Stockholm objectives... and some of the difficulties raised by some participants in their country... ! If we have a quick examination of past/actual situation this should be the first conclusion.

But **despite a reform that could look like a major improvement** some measures seem to have particularly raised some worries from the participants, opening a potential quarrel between supporters of a pure line and defenders of a pragmatic approach.

If we try to pick up the major worries and bring them together under a single call, "quality", they are:

- Minimizing « at school » time
- Reducing length of VET period at a minimum of 6 months
- Opening to private training companies and companies the possibility of creating VET schools (CFA)
-

And going further, this reform is opening a more global thinking about the governance of an apprenticeship system and the role of National Education versus branches and companies.

1. "Quantity versus Quality".

Let's try to discuss the first visible drawback of the reform, we could say "Quantity versus Quality".

By lowering the minimum duration of contract and time spend at school there is probably a positive effect on attractiveness versus transmission of knowledge. This amendment was targeting the high abandon rate (25%). We can surely argue we are choosing numbers and favorite natural tendency of students against school, an easy solution, but we must also know that the government is fighting against "time for time" practice that says that the longer the course, the more efficient the learning. Of course schools like this practice also synonym of "the longer the course, the more money we have"... This approach, cost effectiveness, is now fought by the

government under the pedagogic revolution banner, and the new definition of the training action, we must shorten the learning path if we can arrive to the same progression objective.

Pedagogy is coming upstream and there is probably a large scope of experimentation to make that idea a reality. It should be interesting to investigate more about that topic (suggestion of a workshop participant) but we don't have yet a consistent material.

Enlarging the maximum age to enter into apprenticeship to 30 years can't really be attached to a pedagogic theory. The results of 2018 similar experimentation, weighing 50% of apprenticeship increase in numbers is probably the only reason.

The measures are in fact making closer apprenticeship and Professional VET, shorter, flexible, cheaper...

The discussion came also about the possibility offered to training companies and companies themselves to open their own CFA (apprenticeship school). Isn't that going too far into liberalism option, don't we have the risk to lose the knowledge and experience build by the past system in collaboration with National Education...?

Since Vienna research meeting, an extraordinary and unexpected precision about the vision of the French government came from an interview of the Director of the cabinet of the work Minister, Antoine Foucher. The (real) title was "what would I do with the apprenticeship law if I was a HR Director?". Not only this interview is confirming some participants concerns but it is going further in the liberal possibilities of the law. The best thing to do is to deliver a complete translation of the interview (AEF interview, DÉPÊCHE N°596649) .

"The law will facilitate the establishment of companies CFA "with legal certainty to open and create very simply a CFA for those who have an internal university or even a privileged link with a training organization. Open your CFA now and then you have 18 months to obtain CFA certification, "says Antoine Foucher, pointing out that the law will also help to secure the initiative economically.

"This new framework will make it possible to invest the 13% of the learning tax dedicated to the discharge expenses in the creation of an internal CFA, then it will be possible to use part of the remaining 87% to invest in this structure. An opportunity that should interest the directions of financial affairs of companies, "says Antoine Foucher, making the link with the easing that will allow this new framework.". By internalizing, companies will be able to recruit and train apprentices according to the needs of their 'business model', but also send their apprentices to their subcontractors as in the German model," he continues, adding that this model corresponds rather to big companies.

Another opportunity that will be offered by the reform: establish a privileged partnership with one or more CFA to encourage them to meet the specific needs of the company. "The goal will be for the partner to integrate the needs of the company into their offer, for example by asking them to be able to take in apprentices all year round. It is not on the price but on the quality of the service that it will be necessary to "challenge" the CFA, for example on the duration of the courses which can be too long. If the company does not obtain satisfaction it will be able to see another CFA ", continues Antoine Foucher."

"The third model is the one that will evolve the least, it is to play the competition by using several CFA, to the extent that everyone can adapt in real time to the needs of the company. The first two models are interesting and develop the competitiveness between companies, by increasing the attractiveness of those who invest in these opportunities. The third can work but it is not desirable to limit themselves to compete with the CFA, because it can induce to change all the years of CFA ", Antoine Foucher analysis.

This interview is really designing the way the reform has been imagined: from companies needs to CFA offers, in a very competitive environment where CFA are challenged every year ("it is not a question of price" but it should become if it is just left to companies decision...), and where the apprenticeship tax can be 100% recycled internally by the company! Usually companies have to pay experts to understand how to "optimize" a new law, the solution is given

that time directly by the government! Not only a saving, a sign made to (big) companies, this reform is for you...

A workshop participant has very well summarize the risks linked to this change of paradigm: “ In general, companies and branches think about their own interests rather than creating a comprehensive VET system, so you couldn’t change it so radically without NE strategy (focused on whole system) and control”.

But can’t we imagine a consistent and systemic apprenticeship system without NE control? We must not forget past reproaches made to NE and its lack of understanding of companies ‘needs. The concern could be that we’ve moved from black to white (or white to black) – “a too quick shift from school-based to company-based” - when the governance solution could be grey... A workshop participant is proposing a solution: “the system appears more as an internship program than an apprenticeship program, because the **collective regulation and standardization is missing**”.

Another crucial information given by Antoine Foucher is about quality. As we see efficiency is put ahead, the system will have to make the efforts in terms of certification later.

So, for sure, we can be worried about the quality of apprenticeship training in France. A workshop participant says that “**social responsibility perspective is needed**” to guaranty the **quality of the training**. This is also a good point and there is probably something to include around that notion in the coming decrees for the quality of apprenticeship.

The draft decree for quality lays down the procedures for organizing the control for diplomas issued. Training leading to a professional title is not concerned.

The pedagogical control of apprenticeship training should focus on "the implementation of the training with regard to the reference system of the diploma concerned". It will be carried out "on parts and places of training of apprentices" (companies and CFA).

Each certifying ministry will have to set up a pedagogical control mission for the diplomas which concern it and determine their organization and their mode of operation. The control will be exercised jointly by the following persons:

- inspectors from the certifying ministries (or public officials authorized according to the rules of the ministries concerned);
- the experts designated by the professional branches.
- the experts appointed by the consular chambers. They will be designated "at the request of the regional prefect".

The text specifies that this activity of pedagogical control is "incompatible with a function or a mandate" in a CFA.

These missions will have to transmit each year "a provisional plan of the controls and a report of activity to the prefect of region". The latter will prepare an annual summary report of activities and recommendations. It will be presented to the Regional Committee for Employment, Training and Vocational Guidance.

It is not sure that this project, organizing control by some stakeholders will reassure the advocates of quality...

2. National Education loss of influence

We didn’t spend a lot of time on the articulation of orientation between National Education and entrance in apprenticeship. But it is key for the system.

Amazingly, while NE is losing its influence, it is showing a new dynamism about professionalization. At the very moment when it loses his influence he has never been so successful! To be a bit provocative we could say that branches and companies should inspire of the new collaborative system imagined by NE to boost IVET...

Despite that we must recall two numbers that could justify the preference given to apprenticeship: insertion rate for apprentices (7 months after the end of training) is 67% for

apprenticeship schools and only 48% for professional schools (NE). An expert (Daniel Vatant) is explaining the difference: employers are choosing their apprentices while NE is not choosing its students...! And these figures do not reflect the 25% abandon rate in the apprenticeship system.

In the law, the absolute priority for apprenticeship also translates, unsurprisingly, into a reduction in the financial resources that can be perceived by vocational schools under the apprenticeship tax. The fraction of this tax that can be allocated by employers to vocational training outside apprenticeship is suddenly reduced from 23% to 13%, (a potential loss of resources of the order of 300 M €).

It should also be remembered that the governance of apprenticeship will no longer be the responsibility of the Regions but that of the professional branches. It is of course legitimate, and even necessary, for branches to be actors of learning. But they are not a public service: is learning privatized?

Conclusion

The searchers and participants of the workshop are “pure” defenders of the concepts of VET while in the same time the French Government has made efficiency a priority.

We can just notice that these two worlds are in a way ignoring themselves... One of the participant question was “where does come from or get inspired this reform...?”. Probably not from VET searchers will be my answer, but isn't that a good revelator of our margin of progress in terms of cooperation? Some searchers call to mind that VET liberalization in Poland was a fail and that rebuilding the VET system was not easy after that attempt. From these alerts we can suggest that the first months of the reform should be particularly followed in order to put in place corrective actions if necessary.

I have tried during the workshop to underline the fact that the apprenticeship reform was bringing answers to most past drawbacks, while not minimizing the risks.

Despite that, the reform was not positively received by our group of searchers and experts for the reasons mentioned above.

We can probably regret the lack of exchanges between deciders and the community of specialists of apprenticeship.

But maybe it is not too late to establish a new cooperation model, with a governance including VET specialists.

Anyway, the results of the reform will have to be analyzed with a lot of attention.

Report on the VETNET research workshop
during the third EU Vocational Skills Week in Vienna, 07.11.2018

Vocational education and training across the lifespan

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Introduction

VETNET mission

The Vocational Education and Training Network VETNET is an open network, which welcomes contributions from all over the world as long as they are in line with the goals of VETNET.

VETNET is focusing on research and development in the field of initial, higher and continuing vocational education and training (VET) and learning across the life-span.

The goals of VETNET are to promote research on vocational education and training and to contribute its development by:

- fostering a high quality of research in the field of vocational education and training;
- exploring the relationship between research, policy and practice;
- stimulating the multidisciplinary discussion and dissemination of research results in the European research area and beyond through mutual learning;
- encouraging, establishing and maintaining cooperation between VET researchers and project partnerships in the European research area through, e.g., organising the VETNET programme at the ECER, Crossing Boundaries or Stockholm International Conference; developing international contacts; cooperating with other relevant conferences; publications or by producing electronic or other newsletters;
- maintaining the peer-reviewed VETNET journal IJRNET, the VETNET ECER proceedings and contributing to other international publications; maintaining the community website vetnetsite.org.

VETNET

- maintains a community website on vetnetsite.org;
- has an entry on the EERA website: <https://eera-ecer.de/networks/2-vocational-education-and-training-vetnet/>;
- has a project on [researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net/project/IRNVET-VETNET-International-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training-VETNET-European-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training): <https://www.researchgate.net/project/IRNVET-VETNET-International-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training-VETNET-European-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training>;
- has a community on <https://zenodo.org/communities/vetnet/> to host the conference proceedings.

Aim and scope of the workshop

The topic of the researchers' workshop at the EU Vocational Skills Week 2018 in Vienna was: "Vocational education and training across the lifespan".

All participants contributed to the workshop with a short abstract on the topic "Vocational education and training across the lifespan" and a short bibliography.

Four presentations were selected as impetus presentations. These were short presentations by the authors to stimulate the discussion in the workshop. After the discussion, the presenters of the impetus presentations wrote short minutes on the discussion during the workshop. The impetus presentations and minutes are covered in this report.

Programme of the workshop

Introduction

- Dr Christof Nägele
Senior Researcher, University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Northwestern Switzerland
- Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler
Professor, Institute Technology and Education, University of Bremen
- Mantas Sekmokas
Policy Officer, European Commission, DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion

Impetus Presentations

Lifelong learning and VET: towards understanding the influence of societal eco-systems on learning across the lifespan

- Dr Natalia (Natasha) Kersh
UCL Institute of Education, University of London
- Dr Karen Evans
Professor Emeritus, UCL Institute of Education, University of London

Apprenticeship Reform in France

- Eric Dumartin
Vice-President of Fongecif Île-de-France, Vice-President of IAE Paris I Panthéon Sorbonne

The VET Skills Cycle and the Formation of Construction Management Skills in Ireland

- Eoghan Ó Murchadha
Assistant Head of Department of Craft, Design, Construction and Apprenticeship, Dún Laoghaire Further Education Institute in Dublin

The Role of VET on the Inclusion of Marginalized Young People and Adult People from a Lifelong Perspective across the Lifespan

- Dr Patricia Olmos Rueda
Professor, Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)
- Dr Fernando Marhuenda
Professor, University of Valencia

Outlook

- Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler & Dr Christof Nägele